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PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION AND HPTLC FINGERPRINTING PROFILE OF *MELIA AZEDARACH* LIN AND *PIPER LONGUM*

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ABSTRACT

India has a strong history of traditional herbal system of treatment of various health ailments. In spite of substantial advances in medicinal plant research and rapid advances in modern medicine, there was an increasing problem of liver disorders. The aim of the current study was to perform preliminary phytochemical screening, HPTLC finger printing profile and quantitative analysis of macronutrients, minerals including protein pattern by SDS-PAGE analysis for the various extracts of *Melia azedarach* lin leaves and seeds of *Piper longum* respectively. The study reveals that preliminary phytochemical screening of *Melia azedarach* extract; *Piper longum* extract shows the presence of constituents like alkaloids, carbohydrates, phytosterols, tannins, phenol, flavonoids, glycosides, terpenes, lignin. HPTLC fingerprinting profile and quantitative analysis for both plants of various extracts showed the presence of active components will be responsible for therapeutic activities like antioxidant, anti-emetic, anti-oxidant activity and hepato-protective activity. In future, further studies are needed with these plants to assess, isolate and characterize their pharmacological potentials with their medicinal values.

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient healing system of India, flourished in the Vedic era. According to historical facts, the classical texts of Ayurveda, Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita were written around 1000 B.C. The Ayurvedic Materia Medica includes 600 medicinal plants along with therapeutics^[1]. Herbs like turmeric, fenugreek, ginger, garlic and holy basil are an integral part of Ayurvedic formulations. These formulations incorporate either a single herb or more than one herb (i.e., polyherbal formulations). Before the availability of synthetic drugs, humans were completely dependent on medicinal herbs for prevention and treatment of diseases. The use of the medicinal herbs for curing disease has been documented in the history of all civilizations. The drugs were used in crude forms like expressed juice, powder, decoction or infusion.

Ancient healers who developed formulations based on medicinal herbs were probably not aware of the chemical composition of these herbs. Nevertheless, the advancement they made despite the non-availability of scientific procedures is astonishing. Medicinal plants are a significant source of synthetic and herbal drugs in India and China and have been on the forefront when we talk about history of herbal drugs^[2]. The traditional systems of medicines: Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, Western Herbal Medicine, Traditional Chinese Medicine and Homeopathy have roots in medicinal herbs. Scientific validation of herbal drugs always has been questioned, but with recent advances and publications of clinical trials, the researchers and the public are viewing herbal products with more respect. In the commercial market, medicinal herbs are used as raw drugs, extracts or tinctures. Isolated active constituents are used for applied research^[3].

Standardization and quality control of herbal drugs is a precise complex, because herbal products contain a clutch of phytoconstituents and are very capable of variation. There is the variability within the same plant material or between the different parts of the same plant. The variability may be from grower to grower, crop to crop and also depends on the harvest and post-harvest handling. On the other hand herbal drugs have multiple phytoconstituents including active, inactive, unknown which are dietary rather than therapeutic^[4].

Hence standardization of medicinal plants or herbal drugs like HPTLC finger printing, quantitative analysis are needed to isolate and characterize the active components responsible for its therapeutic activity.

Melia azedarach is well known for its medicinal uses. Its various parts have antihelmintic, antimalarial, cathartic, emetic and emmenagogic properties and are also used to treat skin diseases. It has also been used as an abortifacient, an antiseptic, a purgative, a diuretic, an insect repellent. It is used for generally healing arthritis, rheumatism, for pulmonary disorders, stomach troubles, diarrhoea and dysentery. It is also used as vermifuges to treat, cutaneous, subcutaneous parasitic infection and for menstrual cycle problems^[5].

Piper longum an important medicinal plant belonging to the family of Piperaceae is known as "Thippali" being used in traditional medicine by many people in Asia and Pacific islands especially in Indian medicine. *Piper longum* is a component of medicines reported as good remedy for treating gonorrhoea, menstrual pain, tuberculosis, sleeping problems, respiratory tract infections, chronic gut related pain, and arthritic conditions^[6]. Both *Melia azedarach* and *Piper longum* have immense therapeutic properties especially for the treatment of liver related disorders. But the practice is only at the traditional level because of the lack of experimental proof to standardise the optimum dosage, efficacy and toxic effects.

The present research deals with the phytochemical investigation, development of HPTLC fingerprints and quantitative analysis of *Melia azedarach* leaves and seeds of *Piper longum* respectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plants:

The leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *Piper longum* were collected from the IMPCOPS (Indian Medical practitioners co-operative society, Thiruvanniyur Chennai, India, and were authenticated by Dr. P.T. Kalaichelvan, Professor, Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Chennai, India. The voucher specimen is available in the herbarium file of the Indian Medical Practitioners Co-operative Society, Thiruvanniyur, Chennai, India.

Extraction

Preparation of *Melia azedarach* leaves extract and *Piper longum* Seeds extract

The leaves of *Melia azedarach* (1 kg) and the seeds of *Piper longum* (1 kg) were shade-dried and pulverized to a coarse powder. The powder was passed through 40-mesh sieve and exhaustively extracted with ethyl acetate in soxhlet apparatus at 60°C. The residue left after ethyl acetate extraction was dried and extracted successively with chloroform and ethanol. The extracts were evaporated under reduced pressure using rota flash evaporator till all the solvent had been removed and extract was stored in refrigerator for further use. All these extracts were subjected to HPTLC finger printing analysis.

Preliminary Qualitative Phytochemical Screening

The ethanolic extracts of the MAE, PLE were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening for identification of its active constituents by the method of Kokate *et al.* (1997)^[7].

Test for Alkaloids

A small portion of the solvent free extracts were stirred separately with a few drops of dil. Hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrate may be carefully tested with various alkaloidal reagents.

- (a) Mayer's reagent - Cream precipitate
- (b) Dragondroff reagent - Orange brown precipitate
- (c) Hager's reagent - Yellow precipitate
- (d) Wagner's reagent - Reddish brown precipitate

Test for Carbohydrates

(a) Molisch's Test: The extracts were treated with 2-3 drops of 1% alcoholic alpha naphthol and 2 ml of conc. Sulphuric acid was added along the sides of the test tube carefully. Formation of violet colour ring at the junction of two liquids indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

(b) Fehling's Test: The extracts were treated with Fehling's solution A and B and heated. Appearance of reddish brown colour precipitate indicates the presence of reducing sugars.

(c) Benedict's Test: The extracts were treated with Benedict's reagent and heated. Appearance of reddish orange colour precipitate indicates the presence of reducing sugars.

Test for Proteins

(a) Biuret Test: The extracts were treated with copper sulphate solution, followed by the addition of sodium hydroxide solution appearance of violet colour indicates the presence of proteins.

(b) Millon's Test: When the extracts were treated with Millon's reagent, appearance of pink colour indicates the presence of proteins

Test for Phytosteroids

(a) Libermann Bucharad Test: When the extracts were treated with conc. Sulphuric acid, few drops of glacial acetic acid, followed by the acetic anhydride, there is a formation of violet ring between the two layers, and the appearance of green colour in the aqueous upper layer indicates the presence of steroids.

Test for Phenols

(a) The different extracts were treated with neutral ferric chloride solution. The appearance of violet colour indicates the presence of phenols.

(b) The different extracts were treated with 10% sodium chloride solution. The appearance of cream colour indicates the presence of phenols.

Test for Tannins

(a) When the extracts were treated with 10% lead acetate solution, appearance of white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

(b) When the extracts were treated with aqueous bromine solution, appearance of white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for Flavonoids

(a) 5 ml of the each extract solution was hydrolyzed with 10% v/v sulphuric acid and cooled. Then it was extracted with diethyl ether and divided into three portions in three separate test tubes. 1 ml of diluted sodium carbonate, 1 ml of 0.1N sodium hydroxide and 1ml of strong ammonia solution were added to the first, second and third test tubes respectively. In each test tube, development of yellow colour demonstrated the presence of flavonoids

(b) Shinoda's Test: The extracts were dissolved in alcohol to that one piece of magnesium followed by conc hydrochloric acid was added drop wise and heated. Appearance of magenta colour shows the presence of flavonoids.

Tests for Gums and Mucilage

About 10 ml of various extracts were added separately to 25 ml of absolute alcohol with constant stirring and filtered. The precipitate was dried in air and examined for its swelling properties.

Test for Saponins

(a) Foam Test: 1ml of the different extracts were diluted with distilled water and shaken well in the test tube. The formation of foam in the upper part of the test tube indicates the presence of saponins.

Test for Glycosides

A pinch of the extracts were dissolved in the glacial acetic acid and a few drops of ferric chloride solution were added, followed by the addition of con. Sulphuric acid, formation of red ring at the junction of two liquids indicates the presence of glycosides.

Tests for fixed oils and fats

- (a) Small quantity of the various extracts was separately pressed between two filter papers. Appearance of oil stain on the paper indicates the presence of fixed oil.
- (b) Few drops of 0.5N alcoholic potassium hydroxide were added to small quantity of various extracts along with a drop of phenolphthalein. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 1-2 hours. Formation of soap or partial neutralization of alkali indicates the presence of fixed oils and fats.

Test for Terpenes

When the extracts were treated with tin and thionyl chloride, appearance of pink colour indicates the presence of terpenes.

Test for Lignin

When the extracts were treated with alcoholic solution of phloroglucinol and con. hydrochloric acid appearance of red colour shows presence of lignin.

Estimation of Total Proteins and Macronutrients

The estimation of total proteins present in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *Piper longum* were estimated by using Lowry's *et al.* (1951) method^[8].

High Performance Thin Layer Liquid Chromatography (HPTLC) Finger Printing

HPTLC finger printing was performed on CAMAG TLC scanner-3 instrument, equipped with Linomat IV applicator and CATS 3.2 software. Pre-coated aluminium silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (E. Merck) plates, layer thickness of 0.2 mm were used. Fingerprints were obtained by development in CAMAG twin chamber and were scanned at 254 nm.

Estimation of Total soluble sugars

The estimation of total soluble sugars present in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *piper longum* were estimated by using anthrone method.

Extraction of sugars

For extracting the sugars 1gm of finely powdered sample was suspended in 40 ml of distilled water and heated in the boiling water bath for 30 min. It was centrifuged for 20 min at 3000rpm. The supernatant was collected and the pellet was suspended in 20 ml of water. The extraction steps were repeated 6-8 times till the supernatant was free of sugars.

Estimation of sugars

From the supernatant 1ml of the solution was taken. To that 4 ml of anthrone reagent was added and placed in the boiling water bath for 10 min. Aliquots of standard glucose was also treated in the same way. A blank was set up with 1ml of water. The test tubes were taken out cooled and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 625 nm using the colorimeter. From the standard graph the amount of carbohydrate present in the sample was calculated. The sugar contents of the plant were expressed as mg/100gms of powder.

Estimation of Total Proteins

The estimation of total proteins present in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *Piper longum* were estimated by using Lowry's *et al.* (1951) method.

Extraction of the protein sample

The fresh leaves of the *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *piper longum* were extracted in hot 80% ethanol by macerating in a mortar and pestle. The homogenate was transferred in a centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 2000rpm for 20 min. The supernatant was discarded. The pellet was suspended in a suitable volume of 5% TCA in an ice bath for 15 min. It was centrifuged and the supernatant was discarded. This process was repeated for twice. The pellet was re extracted once with hot absolute ethanol and twice with ethanol: ether mixture, every time discarding the supernatants after centrifugation. This pellet contains the proteins and nucleic acids.

Estimation of the protein sample

Aliquots of the extract were made up to a final volume of 1.0ml with water. A set of standards and blank containing only water were also set up. 5.0ml of alkaline copper reagent was added to all the test tubes, mixed and allowed to stand at room temperature for 10mts. Then 0.5ml of Folin's phenol reagent was added and shaken well. The blue color developed was read at 640nm after 20mts, in the photoelectric colorimeter. The protein contents of the tissues were expressed as mg/100gms of fresh tissue

Estimation of Total lipid

The estimation of Total lipids present in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of *Piper longum* were estimated by using chloroform methanol mixture by the method of Folch *et al.* (1957).

Estimation of Minerals

About 5 – 10gms of oven-dried samples were taken in a silica crucible and heated first in the bunsen burner on a low flame till it gets charred. The silica crucible was transferred to a muffle furnace and heated at dull red heat (500-550°C) till it was completely converted into white ash. The ash was kept in the desiccator containing fused calcium chloride at the bottom, till it gets cooled down. The ash was moistened with small amount of distilled water and 5ml of dilute HCl was added to it. The solution was evaporated to dryness on a boiling water bath and this process was repeated twice. To the extract 4ml of dil.HCl was added and warmed in the boiling water bath. The extract was filtered through what man filter paper and made up to 100ml in the volumetric flask. It was transferred to preacid washed bottles and stored for mineral analysis.

SDS-PAGE analysis of proteins

SDS-PAGE analysis of proteins was performed with the aqueous extracts of the seeds of *Piper longum* and with the leaves of *Melia azedarach*. The molecular weights of the different proteins present in the plants were identified by comparing with the marker proteins.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Preliminary phytochemical screening

In the present investigation preliminary phytochemical screening of the MAE, PLE shows the presence of constituents like alkaloid, carbohydrates, phyto-sterols, tannins, phenol, flavonoids, glycosides, terpenes, lignin. The presence of heavy metals and minerals of the plant extracts evidence for their antioxidant and radical scavenging activity tabulated (Table 1).

Table 1: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of the test drugs.

S.No	Phytochemicals	MAE Extract	PLE Extract
1.	Alkaloid	+	+
2.	Carbohydrate	+	+
3.	Protein	-	-
4.	Phytosterol	+	+
5.	Tannins	+	-
6.	Phenolic compounds	+	+
7.	Flavonoids	+	+
8..	Gums and Mucilage	-	-
9.	Glycosides	+	+
10.	Saponins	-	-
11.	Oils and fats	+	+
12.	Terpenes	+	+
13	Lignin	+	+

(+) indicates the presence of the components, (-) indicates the absence of the components

HPTLC Fingerprinting analysis

In the present investigation, the HPTLC chromatographic pattern of the ethyl acetate extract of *Melia azedarach* showed 9 peaks at Rf values 0.21, 0.29, 0.34, 0.42, 0.57, 0.64, 0.71, 0.85 and 0.92 where as the Chloroform extract of *Melia azedarach* showed 11 peaks at Rf values 0.15, 0.23, 0.29, 0.34, 0.40, 0.43, 0.49, 0.70, 0.73, 0.77 and 0.88. The same plant which was extracted in the ethanol showed 11 peaks at Rf values 0.04, 0.10, 0.36, 0.42, 0.47, 0.56, 0.73 and 0.83 at 254nm which were shown in the Fig.1-3.

Track 1, Analysis a: MELIA (ECA EXT)

Peak #	start			max			end		area	
	Rf	H	[%]	Rf	H	[%]	Rf	H	F	[%]
1	0.02	1.8	21.33	0.05	85.7	21.33	0.21	18.1	6246.9	32.83
2	0.22	17.7	10.00	0.27	40.2	10.00	0.29	36.1	1484.2	7.80
3	0.29	36.1	9.61	0.30	38.6	9.61	0.34	18.0	1134.4	5.96
4	0.34	18.0	7.91	0.38	31.8	7.91	0.42	19.6	1496.7	7.87
5	0.42	19.6	11.78	0.49	47.3	11.78	0.57	11.3	2881.3	15.14
6	0.57	11.3	15.73	0.62	63.2	15.73	0.64	57.7	2107.8	11.08
7	0.64	57.7	15.32	0.66	61.5	15.32	0.71	12.8	2001.2	10.52
8	0.73	15.5	5.67	0.80	22.8	5.67	0.85	10.7	1543.0	8.11
9	0.89	8.2	2.65	0.90	10.7	2.65	0.92	0.2	133.9	0.70

Total height = 401.7 total area = 19029.4

Fig.1: The HPTLC finger print analysis of the Ethyl acetate extract of *M. azedarach*.

Track 2, Analysis b: MELIA (CHCL3 EXT)

Peak #	start			max			end		area	
	Rf	H	[%]	Rf	H	[%]	Rf	H	F	[%]
1	0.02	0.1	13.25	0.06	76.3	13.25	0.15	38.6	5080.4	20.94
2	0.19	32.6	6.22	0.21	35.8	6.22	0.23	34.9	934.1	3.85
3	0.23	34.9	12.41	0.27	71.5	12.41	0.29	57.5	2451.3	10.10
4	0.29	57.5	13.70	0.31	78.9	13.70	0.34	38.0	2289.4	9.44
5	0.34	38.0	9.77	0.37	56.3	9.77	0.40	36.7	1818.4	7.49
6	0.40	36.7	6.59	0.41	38.0	6.59	0.43	28.7	801.0	3.30
7	0.43	28.7	7.60	0.48	43.8	7.60	0.49	40.2	1747.7	7.20
8	0.55	19.3	13.98	0.62	80.5	13.98	0.70	26.1	6072.2	25.03
9	0.70	26.1	5.03	0.72	29.0	5.03	0.73	28.1	640.9	2.64
10	0.73	28.1	5.74	0.75	33.1	5.74	0.77	32.2	873.5	3.60
11	0.77	32.2	5.72	0.78	33.0	5.72	0.88	0.0	1553.1	6.40

Total height = 576.0 total area = 24262.1

Fig.2: The HPTLC finger print analysis of the Chloroform extract of *Melia Azedarach*.

Fig.3: The HPTLC finger print analysis of the Ethanolic extract of *Melia Azedarach*.

The HPTLC finger printing ethyl acetate extract of *Piper longum* showed 11 peaks at Rf values 0.03, 0.08, 0.13, 0.23, 0.30, 0.40, 0.51, 0.61, 0.76, 0.88 and 0.94 where as the Chloroform extract showed 10 peaks at Rf values 0.09, 0.16, 0.24, 0.32, 0.53, 0.63, 0.77, 0.86 and 0.94. The ethanolic extract of the same plant showed 12 peaks at Rf values 0.03, 0.06, 0.11, 0.19, 0.27, 0.37, 0.47, 0.59, 0.69, 0.80, 0.86 and 0.92 at 254nm (Fig.4-6).

Peak #	start		max			end		area	
	Rf	H	Rf	H	[%]	Rf	H	F	[%]
1	0.00	0.2	0.01	12.5	2.05	0.03	0.0	138.9	0.48
2	0.03	1.1	0.06	45.3	7.44	0.06	39.3	729.0	2.52
3	0.06	39.3	0.07	44.9	7.37	0.11	24.7	1147.2	3.96
4	0.11	24.4	0.14	31.7	5.21	0.19	18.8	1537.5	5.31
5	0.19	18.8	0.24	36.4	5.97	0.27	27.9	1945.0	6.71
6	0.27	27.9	0.31	43.5	7.15	0.37	15.2	2217.1	7.65
7	0.37	15.2	0.42	73.4	12.06	0.47	62.2	4544.2	15.68
8	0.47	62.2	0.48	63.5	10.42	0.59	16.1	4045.0	13.96
9	0.59	16.1	0.66	58.1	9.55	0.69	43.6	2955.3	10.20
10	0.69	43.6	0.75	75.7	12.43	0.80	58.0	5493.2	18.96
11	0.80	58.0	0.83	67.7	11.11	0.86	30.9	2652.8	9.15
12	0.86	30.9	0.90	56.2	9.24	0.92	0.0	1572.7	5.43

Total height = 609.0 total area = 28977.9

Fig.6: The HPTLC finger print analysis of the ethanolic extract of *Piper longum*.

The SDS-PAGE electrophoresis results of aqueous extract of *Melia azedarach* showed the presence of protein bands with molecular weight of ranging 6.50 - 97.4 kDa were shown in Fig 7. The *Piper longum* seeds showed only two protein bands in the molecular weight of 30 and 60 kDa.

Fig 7: SDS-PAGE electrophoresis results of aqueous extract of *Melia azedarach*.

Lane 1 - shows the marker protein bands with their molecular weight ranging 6.50 – 97.4 kDa. Lane 2 - shows the *Melia azedarach* leaf protein bands with their molecular weight of ranging 6.50 – 97.4 kDa. Protein used as markers with their molecular weight expressed in kDa: Phosphorylase b-97.4; BSA-66; Ovalbumin-43; Carbonic Anhydrase-29; Soyabean; Trypsin Inhibitor-20.1; Lysozyme-14.3; Aprotinin-6.5.

The values of the macronutrients like carbohydrates, proteins and lipids present in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* and seeds of the *Piper longum*. The carbohydrate content present in the seeds of the *piper longum* is 13.56mg / 100gms, whereas the leaves of *Melia azedarach* contain 23.78mg / 100 gms. The protein content was also found to be high in the leaves of *Melia azedarach* when compared with the seeds of *Piper longum*. The same was applicable to the lipid content also, in which the leaves of *Melia azedarach* contained 27.94 mg/ 100 gms and *Piper longum* contained 3.78mg/ 100gms respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Concentration of Macronutrients.

S.No.	Macronutrients	Leaves of <i>Melia azedarach</i> (Expressed in mg/100gms)	Seeds of <i>Piper longum</i> (Expressed in mg/100gms)
1.	Total sugars	23.78	13.56
2.	Total protein	36.23	7.80
3.	Total lipid	27.94	3.78

The concentration of different minerals like Ca, K, Na, Mg, Zn, Si, Fe, Al, Va, Mb, Cu, Ni, Hg, Pb, Ba, Mn, Cr, Co and Se expressed in PPM. The concentration of these minerals in *Melia azedarach* leaves was found to be in the following order. Ca, > K, > Na, > Mg, > Zn, > Si, > Fe, > Al, > Va, > Mb, > Cu, > Ni, > Hg, > Pb, > Ba, > Mn, > Cr, > Co > and Se. From the values it was clear that the leaves of *Melia azedarach* has got a high calcium content and has a low content of selenium. At the same time the concentration of these minerals in the seeds of *piper longum* was found to be in the following order, Ca, > K, > Na, > Mg, > Zn, > Fe, > Al, > Va, > Si, > Cu, > Mb, > Ba, > Hg, > Ni, > Cr, > Mn, > Co, > Pb > and Se. Here also the *Piper longum* seeds contain highest content of calcium and lowest content of selenium (Table 3).

Table 3: Concentration of Minerals present in the plants.

S.No.	Macronutrients	Leaves of <i>Melia azedarach</i> (Expressed in PPM)	Seeds of <i>Piper longum</i> (Expressed in PPM)
1.	Aluminum	3.286	2.294
2.	Barium	0.299	0.420
3.	Calcium	280	340
4.	Copper	0.746	0.574
5.	Chromium	0.186	0.149
6.	Cobalt	0.107	0.081
7.	Iron	2.198	2.633
8.	Lead	0.311	0.025
9.	Magnesium	36.171	26.115
10.	Molybdenum	0.810	0.745
11.	Mercury	0.371	0.259
12.	Manganese	0.136	0.132
13.	Nickel	0.429	0.181
14.	Potassium	136.5	117
15.	Sodium	92	138
16.	Silicon	2.343	1.399
17.	Selenium	0.0117	0.0094
18.	Vanadium	1.2945	2.107
19.	Zinc	4.944	4.130

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening of chemical constituents of the test drugs showed that the leaves of *M. azedarach* and seeds of *P. longum* were rich in alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, terpenoids glycosides and lignins. It is generally accepted that a synergistic relationship amongst phytochemicals has been adduced to be responsible for the overall beneficial effect derivable from plants. It was stated by Costa *et al* in 1999 that phytochemicals accumulate in different parts of the plants, such as in the roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits or seeds^[9]. According to Hill *et al* (1952) most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds which are found in our plant to a considerable amount. They were known to show medicinal activity as well as exhibiting physiological activity^[10].

HPTLC fingerprint analysis not only gives the idea for the substantiation of the plant extracts and its components but also provides the factors responsible for eminence of herbal formulations. In addition to qualitative detection, HPTLC technique also provides semi-quantitative evidence about the key active phytoconstituents present in a plant extract, thus supporting a valuation of plant extract quality^[11].

Micronutrients consist of vitamins and minerals required by the body in small quantities for the normal function of cellular metabolic processes. They usually function as essential cofactors in the numerous enzyme catalyzed reactions and their absence can result in impairment of metabolic functions, which can lead to serious disease conditions. Electrolyte disturbances may lead to severe and even life-threatening metabolic abnormalities such as liver diseases, one associated with abnormal serum sodium concentrations, with hyponatremia as the most common alteration^[12]. Sodium together with potassium assists in the maintenance of the body's electrolyte and water balance. In addition, potassium and sodium play an important role, in transmission of nerve impulses, muscle contraction, and the transport of substances across membranes. As mentioned by Damodara Reddy (2007) supplementation of plant extracts to CCl₄ rats significantly maintained acid-base balance probably by increasing the absorption of electrolytes and minerals from intestine and inhibited electrolytes elimination through urine. The same effect can be expected in our study also because the plant extracts under present investigation contains these minerals^[13].

The presence of selenium in minute quantities in our plant might be responsible for its hepatoprotective activity. Selenium and vitamin E work together synergistically in that they carry out antioxidant and immuno stimulating function better together than individually. The main function of selenium is to act as a cofactor in the enzyme selenium-glutathione peroxidase which is considered as an *in vivo* antioxidant enzyme in protecting the cells from free radicals. The antioxidant properties of selenoproteins help to prevent cellular damage from free radicals, regulate thyroid function and play a role in immune system as reported by Hana Střítecká *et al* 2010^[14].

The mineral analysis of the test drugs showed the presence of zinc. Zinc is widely recognized as an essential micronutrient with a catalytic role in over 100 specific metabolic enzymes in human metabolism. It is one of the most ubiquitous of all trace elements involved in human metabolism and plays multiple roles in the perpetuation of genetic materials including transcription of DNA, translation of RNA, and ultimately in cellular division. So supplementation of zinc in the form of plant drug would be helpful in maintaining the normal metabolism of the cells^[15].

Calcium salts provide rigidity to the skeleton and calcium ion plays a role in many if not most, metabolic processes. Many neuromuscular and other cellular functions depend on the maintenance of the ionized calcium concentration in the extracellular fluid. Calcium fluxes are important mediators of hormonal effects on target organs through several intracellular signalling pathways (FAO/WHO, 1998). Phosphorous is also important in bone formation and many essential metabolic activities in the body such as phosphorylation reactions. As reported by Claudia Sissi and Manlio Palumbo *et al.* (2009), Mg plays an important role in the metabolism of calcium. Soft tissue magnesium functions as a cofactor of many enzymes involved in energy metabolism, protein synthesis, RNA and DNA synthesis, and maintenance of the electrical potential of nervous tissue and cell membranes^[16]. The presence of these minerals in the plant extract might be responsible for the overall free radical scavenging properties. The important minerals and vitamin found in the plant might also be major contributors to the medicinal value of the plant. Mineral elements may have more roles to play, than presently acknowledged, in the synergy of phytochemicals for the health benefit of man.

The presence of different proteins in the leaves of *M. azedarach* and seeds of *P. longum* also document some evidence towards hepatoprotective activity against the free radical damage on liver. Plants have been actively targeted for the production of medically important proteins, including vaccine antigens and monoclonal antibodies especially against Hepatitis viruses^[17]. So, by future investigations any one of the protein present in the plants can be targeted for the development of vaccines against liver diseases.

CONCLUSION

Over the past decade, there has been a resurrection of interest in the exploration of medicinal plant as a source of prospective herbal medicine. There is a need to advance research for the development, characterization of new natural drugs with the assist of better drugs from its constituents from plants and other natural sources. HPTLC fingerprint analysis can be used as a diagnostic tool for the correct identification of the plant. Though, further works are mandatory to depict further chemical constituents and performing quantitative estimation with marker compounds is also indispensable along with the other values for fixing standards to this plant. The study concludes that preliminary phytochemical, quantitative analysis and HPTLC fingerprinting profile of *Melia azedarach* Lin and *Piper longum* reveals the presence of active components responsible for therapeutic activities like antioxidant, anti-emetic, anti-oxidant activity, and hepato-protective activity. In future, further studies are needed with these plants to assess their pharmacological potentials, isolate, characterize and elucidate the structures of the bioactive compounds responsible for their therapeutic activities and other medicinal values for better health care.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS:

HPTLC	: High performance thin layer liquid chromatography
MAE	: <i>Melia azedarach</i> leaves extract, PLE: <i>Piper longum</i> Seeds extract
SDS-PAGE analysis	: Sodium dodecylsulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

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